

**THE IMPORTANCE OF DOWNLOADS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
PHYSICAL FITNESS OF YOUNG TABLE TENNIS PLAYERS**

Yo‘dashaliyeva Muslima Izzatali qizi

Uzbek state university of physical education and sports

St-51-21 Group student

Annotation

This article describes the role of auxiliary physical exercises in the development of physical fitness of young table tennis players, their use and the tasks that need to be solved with these exercises, as well as information and practical recommendations on the importance of loads given to the body.

Key words: physical fitness, general and special physical fitness, physical qualities, auxiliary exercises, strength, agility, agility, endurance, flexibility.

Аннотация

В данной статье описывается роль вспомогательных физических упражнений в развитии физической подготовленности юных игроков в настольный теннис, их использование и задачи, которые необходимо решать с помощью этих упражнений, а также информация и практические рекомендации о важности нагрузок, даваемых организму.

Ключевые слова: физическая подготовка, общая и специальная физическая подготовка, физические качества, вспомогательные упражнения, сила, ловкость, проворство, выносливость, гибкость.

Relevance of the topic. Today, the development of physical fitness of young table tennis players is considered one of the most important components of sports training and is understood as a process aimed at the comprehensive development of the body, strengthening health, improving physical abilities and creating a solid functional base for all other types of training, as well as achieving high results in sports.

High demands are placed on the development of physical fitness in the sport of Table tennis.

This can be explained by the following factors:

- The growth of achievements in sports always requires a new level of development of physical abilities from an athlete;
- A high level of physical fitness is a prerequisite for increasing training and competition loads.

According to the nature and direction of action of the means used, the physical fitness of young table tennis players is studied by dividing them into general physical training, auxiliary and special physical training groups.

The general physical fitness of young table tennis players is the foundation, the necessary basis for achieving high results. It is aimed at solving the following tasks.

- Increasing the functionality of the body of young table tennis players;
- Physical qualities – development of strength, agility, endurance, agility and flexibility;
- Elimination of defects in the physical development of the body of young table tennis players.

The auxiliary physical training of young table tennis players is designed to provide the necessary functional basis for effective activities aimed at the development of special physical abilities. It has a special focus and is aimed at solving the following tasks:

- Development of the functionality of young table tennis players, which is manifested in action activities specific to the chosen sport;
- Improving my organization's high level of special load resistance as well as agility and agility skills;
- Increased severity of recovery processes.

The special physical training of young table tennis players is aimed at the development of physical abilities in the chosen sport with strict adherence to the requirements set by the features of the competition's activities.

Special physical training of young table tennis players solves the following tasks:

- improving physical abilities inherent in the chosen sport;
- development with a deepening of the movement skills necessary for successful technical and tactical improvement in the chosen sport;
- selective development of individual muscle groups that are more involved in performing specialized exercises.

The special physical training of young table tennis players is directed to the development of the most important action qualities in the system of movement skills. Therefore, competition exercises are used as the main tools of special physical training and are used in combination with various complicating elements that enhance their effect on the athlete's body.

All types of physical fitness have certain similarities. The physical fitness of young table tennis players is closely related to sports specialization. Failure to adequately assess some type of physical fitness during the exercise process will ultimately prevent increased sports skills. In the training of young table tennis players, the tasks assigned to the ratio of general physical fitness and special physical training tools are changed depending on the age, qualifications of athletes, their individual characteristics, stages and periods of the training process, the state of the body at the moment.

As the athlete's qualifications increase, the contribution of special physical training tools increases, and the volume of general physical training tools decreases accordingly.

In addition, the formation of the physical culture of young table tennis players is also an important factor. Therefore, those who are engaged in the process of forming the physical culture of young athletes not only master the movements and the knowledge associated with them, but also develop their own physical abilities. Currently, the terms "physical abilities" and "physical qualities" are used to describe the movement capabilities of athletes. Although these concepts are similar in a certain sense, but are not identical. Physical abilities are a complex of mental-physiological

and morphological characteristics of a young athlete that meet the requirements of one or another muscle activity and ensure its effective performance. In physical education and sports, the characteristics characteristic of the quality of the abilities of athletes are reflected in the phrases “strong”, “fast”, “agile”, “flexible”, “resistant”.

Currently, it is accepted to excite physical abilities into five main types: strength, agility and coordination skills, endurance and flexibility. Each of them is manifested in different forms of movement activity in different types.

Currently, there are also Basic Laws for the development of physical abilities:

1. Movement is the leading factor in physical abilities.
2. Dependence of the development of abilities on the mode of action activity.
3. Staging of the development of physical abilities.
4. Uneven and heterochrony of the development of abilities (belonging to different times).
5. Return of abilities indicators.
6. Displacement of physical abilities.
7. Interaction and unity of movement skills and physical abilities.

Due to this, the degree to which young table tennis players acquire this or that activity of movement to the extent that they are able to develop appropriate physical abilities also changes. Therefore, the person conducting the pedagogical process in the field of physical education will have to build it in accordance with the principles of the development of physical abilities, and not just the principles of education and training. In this case, it should be taken into account that the principles of training in physical exercises embody the only requirements in rhythmic gymnasts: in them, any pedagogical process should be built on the basis of awareness, activity and other principles. But the exact realization of these principles must comply with the solved tasks.

Thus, the actual indicators of the maximum load can be determined only by the ratio of those involved to a specific physical condition.

Of course, in the development of physical abilities, it is necessary to apply the maximum loads in the presence of appropriate training in those who are engaged, taking into account their age, individual characteristics, as well as specific aspects of the load, observing other tamoils. The size of the physical load is characterized by its size and intensity. Accordingly, it is permissible to accurately distribute the load workload.

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